

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The impact of Boko haram insurgency on social orientation and academic performance of secondary school students in Potiskum Local Government

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Abstract

The study was designed to investigate the Impact of Boko Haram Insurgency on Social Orientation and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Potiskum Local Government. The three major objectives that guided the study were to evaluate the number and rate of students' dropout due to the Boko Haram insurgent, to investigate the rate of students' enrolment in secondary school and to Evaluate Teachers performance during book haram insurgent. The study employed descriptive survey research design and the instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed in consonance with the review of available literature on the study under investigation. The data collected from the questionnaire items were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis of the study at 0.05 level of significance. Decision for accepting or rejecting an item or group of items was based on cut-off point of 2.50. Based on research question one, the finding of the study revealed that crises has all effect on school attendance of both the teachers and students, destruction of available facilities of the schools influence the well-being of students in classroom; loss of teachers due to the crisis in the area influences the well-being of student in classroom, damaging school infrastructure can grossly reduce the availability of access to education which reduces performance, insurgents suicide bombings at school as a tactics which in turn reduce school population and affect the academic performance of students, destruction of available school facilities by insurgents leaves the educational system in a dire situation, insecurity in the state insurgents have leads to the deaths of many students, killing and abduction of students by the has been traumatic for students as they are forced to flee their homes in fear. The attack by the insurgents include fear and reduce academic performance and violence can affect attendance and learning cannot successfully occurs in an environment of fear and some of the influences of schools as insecurity constitutes a negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that Boko Haram insurgents consequently, developed threat on social well-being of students in secondary schools Potiskum local government area of Yobe State.

Keywords: Boko-Haram; Insurgency; Students; Social Orientation; Impact; academic; Performance

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1. Introduction

The nation Nigeria witnessed brutal confrontation and massive assault from terrorist group which is undoubtedly the most blood-thirsty and destructive, both in term of demonic brutality, mindless savagery and flagrant disobedience to the principles of peace and stability. Nigeria has witnessed insurgency from this terrorist group called Boko Haram from 2009. They unleash terrorist group called Boko Haram from 2009. They unleash terror and fear in the minds of every Nigeria. There is wanton destruction of government properties, bombing of churches, mosques and other public places, assassination of prominent individuals, burning of schools occasioned by sporadic shooting of innocent citizens.

Insurgencies has been as old as civilization but became most prominent after the September 11, 2001 bombing of the United States by Al-Qaeda, the bombings were carried out on world trade centre which has adverse effects on the education and business activities or America and globally [1]. Other insurgent's activities were carried out by other groups such Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb of Algeria and Al-Shabaab of Somalia which also affects the education as well the economy of those countries. Insurgency as defined Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary (2008) is the rebellion or revolt, that's the state of being insurgent.

Boko Haram also known as the Jama'atu Ahlus Sunna Lidda Awati Wal- Jihad started as a small radical Sunni Islamic organization with preaching and a limited support from among the Sufi Islamic communities in the northeastern part of Nigeria, the anti-western ideology of the Book Haram terrorist group, earn it the concern about its potential relationship with other groups such as Sunni extremist or terrorist groups elsewhere, including al-Qaeda a swell as al-Qaeda affiliates such as al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) in Algeria and Mali and Al-Shabaab in Somalia. There groups bomb schools, shopping malls; airports and business areas, thereby making education and business environment to collapse [2].

In Hausa language, Book Haram means western education is an abomination or forbidden. This group was founded by a Nigerian named Mohammed Yusuf in the year 1995. As a Muslim sect that intends to abolish secular of government and establish Sharia law in Nigeria [3]. It is an offshoot of a radical Islamic youth group which worshipped at the Alhaji Muhammad Ndimi mosque in Maiduguri, in the 1990s.

What today can be considered as a security monster could be traced to the teachings the Maitasine, Mohammed Marwa and a Muslim fundamentalist that rejected the impact of education system imposed by the British when they conquered the Sokoto caliphate in 1903 [3,4]. Like the members of the Ja'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda Wati Wal-Jihad, which is the original name of Boko Haram meaning "people committed to the propagation of the prophet's teachings and Jihad" they strictly believed in the Qur'an phrase surah 4:11 "Anyone who is not governed by what Allah has revealed is among the transgressors. Hence members of these sects believed that it is 'Haram' or 'sinful' to embrace western education as it is not revealed by the prophet.

Education is worst hit by the Boko Haram activities. Apart from the fact that the fight is directly against western education which is widely practiced in Nigeria with schools established in every nook and cranny of the country, western education has remained the bedrock of human and capital developments in Nigeria. Education is under attack, as incidents of violence against students, teachers, union, schools and government officials are on the rise worldwide and in Nigeria particularly. Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria, deliberate threat against students, academics, teachers and educational facilities create barrier to accessing quality education. Education is a right, like the right to have proper food or roof over one's head. Education is not only a right bust passport to human development. It opens door and expands opportunities and freedom. It contributes to fostering peace, democracy and economic growth as well as improving health and reducing poverty. The current Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria is threatening to halt or even reverse this progress. Education is under attack in northern Nigeria particularly in Yobe State.

Despite the imbalance in education in the northern and southern Nigeria, while the northern embraced Islamic education, the south practiced western education after the amalgamation of the northern and southern protectorates in 1914, western education became a unifying force for the two regions. So, the northern Nigeria was to some extent disadvantaged as they embraced western education late. The Almajiri education system which started in northern Nigeria around the eleventh century A.D. [5] involve sending male children to faraway places to acquire Islamic education at a tender age of four to nine years. Its success in the past was because the host community took responsibility for the children's welfare. Today the Almajiri's are left at the mercy of their teachers or instructors who convert them into street beggars. [5]disclosed that in April, 2012 that there were over 9.5 million Almajiri children that are denied to right to basic primary education in Nigeria.

Northern Nigeria has suffered low enrolment rate especially at the primary education sector. [6] blamed this on the effect of long standing effect of Islamic education as most parents are yet to embrace western education. To such parents, western education is tied to the bible and it is an indirect way to changing their religion. Secondly, the security situation in the northern Nigeria also comes to play. The constant threat posed by Boko Haram which started in 2009 and other extremists religious sect like the Jama'atu Anbarul Muslimna Finbadilas Suda, undermines efforts at improving education in the region. These groups have carried out several attacks and issued threats to schools in the north in some of these attacks, teachers were liked or injured and structure razed. In September, 2013 a school of agriculture in Yobe state was attacked at night by the Boko Haram and more than sixty students were killed [7;8] also a secondary school in Mamudo town of Potiskum where more than thirty students were slaughtered, also a massacre of over four hundred people (male, female and children) at Potiskum cattle market and suicide bombing attack in Government Science and Technical College Potiskum which kills over sixty-three students and injured many among others. These are among the several attacks on schools by the Boko Haram. Longer-term impact of persistent targeted violent attacks, including the destruction of schools and the killing of students, teachers and other education personnel, on education systems is very patchy. The fear or trauma reduces the quality of education provision and students' ability to learn, thereby leads to poor academic performance by the students.

The social orientation effects of Boko Haram attacks have both symbolic and ideological effects on education which exacerbate the physical effects. According to [9], the special reporter on the right to education argues that the symbolic effect is the promulgation of fear, subordination to others and the ideological effects is the removal of right to education and the denial of its purpose. The destruction of large numbers of schools or sexual violence against school girls is a rejection of the right of women. The result can be downgrading of women's position in society and a widespread abandonment of education by students, teachers and governments and the consequent dilapidation and collapse of educational infrastructure and dwindling of expertise on a scale that fuel loss of faith in government and set back in development.

Persistent attacks can lead to large numbers of schools being closed for a year or a number of years, or to large numbers of students being withdrawn from school by their parents. Students worried or anxious about attacks on their school or others nearby may find it hard to concentrate in class, which will affect their ability to learn. The cumulative effect of teacher and student distraction, lost days due to closures, teacher shortages, and failure to repair damage to schools is likely to cause falling levels of achievement when these factors persist over long periods of time. [10] maintained that one of the more extensively reported factors affecting students' academic performance is infrastructure where most of it have being set ablaze by the insurgents.

2. Statement of the Problem

Academic activities are disrupted intermittently as a result of sporadic attacks on education facilities. Government has had to shut down schools in order to forestall sudden attacks on them by insurgents. The Boko Haram attacks culminate in poor student's performance because learning is characterized by threat in the school environment of the north particularly in Potiskum local government area, Yobe state whereas it is an accomplished fact that learning thrives mostly in an environment devoid of threat. [8] asserted that "any society characterized by any form of violence will not be conducive for any social interaction in form of teaching and learning". Similarly it has been noted that the threat of insecurity will constitute negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that teaching and learning cannot occur successfully in an environment characterized by threat [13]. There are series of case bombing and burning of schools and houses in northern Nigeria particularly in Potiskum which include; suicide bombing attack in Government Science and Technical College of Potiskum which kills over twenty-six (26) students died in the attack and more than 81 students suffered minor to grievous injuries, Mamudo town of Potiskum where more than thirty students were slaughtered and school of Agriculture in Yobe state was attacked at night by the Boko Haram which more than sixty students were killed. Therefore, it is based on these facts that the researchers intends to investigate the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance in affected secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe state.

2.1. Justification of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance of the student in some affected secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe State, due to the fact that academic activities are disrupted intermittently as a result of sporadic attacks on secondary schools education facilities, which lead the government to shut down secondary schools education in order to forestall sudden attacks on them by boko haram insurgents. In line with the forgoing, Etebu and James (2011) asserted that "any society characterized by any form of violence will not be conducive for any social interaction and insecure for teaching and learning atmosphere.

2.2. Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance in affected secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe state. Specifically, the study sought to:

Find out the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation well-being of students in some selected secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe State.

Determine the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area.

To proffered the ways forward to the impact of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area.

2.3. Objectives of the Study

The impact of Boko Haram on Social Orientation and Academic Performance of the Student in some affected secondary School in Potiskum Local Government area of Yobe state.

- To evaluate the number and rate of students dropout due to the Boko Haram insurgent.
- To investigate the rate of students enrolment in secondary school.
- To Evaluate Teachers performance during book haram insurgent.

2.4. Research Questions

Three questions were formulated to guide the study.

What are the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation well-being of students in some secondary school in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State?

What are the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area?

What are the ways forward on the impact of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area?

2.5. Research Hypothesis

The null hypothesis developed would be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female respondents on the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance in affected secondary schools in Potiskum local government area of Yobe state.

2.6. Significance of the Study

The research work gives a clear view on the re-orientation of the masses especially in the northern part of Nigeria on the importance of education, it also discuss the roles peace and stability on the academic performance of the student. The study will also highlight the factors affecting the level of academic performance among students in Yobe south. The student will reveal the effect of bombing, burning of school and houses on the academic performance of students in Potiskum, Yobe State. The study would be useful to government and stakeholders in solving the persistent problem of insurgency that has crippled the educational sector and performance of students in the state.

Findings of this study will also benefit researchers by adding to the pool of information that already exists in this area. Researchers can therefore fall back on information gathered here by replicating this study in another setting.

2.7. Design of the Study

This study employed descriptive survey research design, descriptive survey is a study which is aimed at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about given population. [10] Stated that survey design is used in a situation where the study employs questionnaire to determine opinion, preference, attitude and perception of people about an issue. Descriptive survey design is therefore considered appropriate for this study

since it sought to assess the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance affected secondary schools of Potiskum area of Yobe State.

2.8. Area of the Study

The study will be carried out in Potiskum area of Yobe State and only the affected secondary schools should be considered from Potiskum, Nangere, Fika and Fune: thus

2.9. Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of the entire teachers and students in secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe State.

Table 1 List of schools involved and the population of the students

S/n	Schools	Population of students
1	Government Girls Science and technical College Potiskum	3,021
2	Government Science and Technical College Potiskum	2,639
3	Fika Government Secondary School	2,346
4	Government secondary school Mamudo	1,873
5	Government Day secondary school Potiskum	4,363
	Total	14,233

Zonal office Potiskum: (2019)

3. Sample and Sampling Techniques

Simple random sampling was employed for the study which comprises of one hundred and fifty (150) students were randomly selected from five (5) secondary schools in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State.

3.1. Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed in consonance with the review of available literature on the study under investigation. The instrument titled "Impact of Boko Haram on Social Orientation and Academic Performance in affected schools in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State" was developed to elicit information from the respondents. The instrument was structured in a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with number values of 4,3,2 and 1 respectively assigned.

3.2. Validation of the Instrument

The validity of the instrument for this study was established through face validation. According to Uju (2011), face validation judges at the face value, the appropriateness of the evaluating instrument. There should be no confusing words in the items. Draft copies of the instrument was given to three (3) experts for validation, comment and advices. The experts were made up of the researchers' supervisor and two other lecturers from school of Technical Education and School of Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Potiskum.

3.3. Method of Data Collection

The questionnaires were administered to the respondents by the researchers. The researchers make to ensure of immediate completion and return of the completed questionnaires by going round to collect the completed questionnaires.

3.4. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire items were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis of the study at 0.05 level of significance. Decision for accepting or rejecting an item or group of items was based on cut-off point of 2.50 therefore, any item greater than or equal to 2.50 was considered agreed while less than or equal to 2.49 were considered disagreed.

4. Results

4.1. Research Question 1

What are the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation of well-being students in affected secondary school in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State?

Table 1 The mean and standard deviation on influences of Boko Haram on social well-being of students in secondary schools Potiskum local government area.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	X	SD	Remarks
1	Crises has an effect on school attendance of both the teachers and students	29	36	14	11	-	3.92	0.99	Agreed
2	Destruction of available facilities in the schools influences the well-being of students in classroom	23	44	0	14	-	3.84	0.98	Agreed
3	Loss of teachers due to the crises in the area influences the well-being of students in classroom	15	44	20	11	-	3.70	0.89	Agreed
4	Damaging school infrastructure can grossly reduce the availability of access to education which reduces performance	17	67	4	2	-	4.10	0.56	Agreed
5	Insurgencies suicide bombings at school as a tactics which in turn reduce school population and affect the academic performance of students	30	43	7	4	6	3.97	1.08	Agreed
6	Destruction of available school facilities by insurgents leaves the educational system in a dire situation	19	27	22	12	10	3.37	1.27	Agreed
7	Insecurity bin the state has been traumatic for students as they are forced to flee their homes in fear	31	31	13	5	10	3.76	1.29	Agreed
8	The attack by the insurgents have leads to the deaths of many students	27	40	13	6	4	3.89	1.05	Agreed
9	Killing and abduction of students by the insurgents induce fear and reduce academic performance	20	48	12	7	3	3.83	0.97	Agreed
10	Violence can affect attendance schools as insecurity constitutes a negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that teaching and learning cannot successfully occurs in an environment of fear	41	33	10	3	3	4.18	0.99	Agreed

From table 1 above, the findings of the study revealed that all of the respondent agreed with the statements that, crises has an effect on schools attendance of both the teachers and students, destruction of available facilities in the schools influences the well-being of student in classroom, loss of teachers due to the crises in the area influences the well-being of student in classroom, damaging school infrastructure can grossly reduce the availability of access to education which reduces performance, insurgents suicide bombings at school as a tactics which in turn reduce school population and affect the academic performance of students, destruction of available school facilities by insurgents leaves the educational system in a dire situation; insecurity in the state has been traumatic for students as they are forced to flee their homes in tear, the attack by the insurgents have leads to the deaths of many students, killing and abduction of students by the insurgents induce fear and reduce academic performance and violence can affect attendance in schools

as insecurity constitutes a negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that teaching and learning cannot successfully occurs in an environment of fear are some of the influences of Boko Haram on social well-being of students in secondary schools in Potiskum Local Government Area.

4.2. Research Question: 2

What are the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area?

Table 2 The mean and standard deviation on the influences of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	X	SD	Remarks
1	Attack on one school/locality leads to fear that any school in the area might be attacked	31	47	3	7	2	4.09	0.94	Agreed
2	Many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety which affect academic performance	35	39	14	1	1	4.18	0.72	Agreed
3	Psychosocial impact of the attacks insurgents affect students ability to learn	24	41	17	6	2	3.88	0.96	Agreed
4	The threat of attacks persists may lead to the students being kept at home which in turn affect their performance	25	43	10	6	6	3.83	1.11	Agreed
5	The targeted attacks at school during insurgencies and the general state of insecurity could force the school to closed	23	46	15	5	3	3.92	0.93	Agreed

From table 2 above, the findings of the study further revealed that all of the respondents also agreed with the statements that, attack on one school/locality leads to fear that any school in the area might be attacked, many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety which affect academic performance, psychosocial impact of the attacks of insurgents affect students ability to learn, threat of attacks persists may lead to the students being kept at home which in turn affect their performance and that the targeted attacks at school during insurgencies and the general state of insecurity could force the school to closed are some of the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area.

4.3. Research Question 3

What are the .ways forward to the impact of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area?

From table 3, the findings of the study also revealed that all of the respondents agreed with the statements that, insurgents (Boko harams) and other armed groups to cease all unlawful killings, including targeted attacks on teachers, school students, state government should provide government should renovate all schools damaged in the state as a result of them violence and ensure that they are provided with adequate teaching staff, federal government adequate security to prevent attacks on schools buildings, teachers and school, students/pupils, on their part should provide adequate support to the affected stated by expeditiously rebuild and renovate all school building and facilities destroyed during the attacks and ability to provide all necessary support to all those, including teachers and students, who have been affected by violence which include rehabilitation and resettlement for those who have force to flee the violence are some of the ways forward to the impact of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area.

Table 3 The means and standard deviation on the ways forward to the influence of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	X	SD	Remarks
6	Insurgents (Boko Harams) and other armed groups of cease all unlawful killings, including targeted attacks on teachers, school students	24	44	9	8	5	3.82	1.10	Agreed
7	State government should provide adequate security to prevent attacks on school buildings, teachers and school students/pupils	33	40	10	2	5	4.04	1.04	Agreed
8	Government should renovate all school damaged in the state as a result of them violence and ensure that they are provided with adequate teaching staff	33	37	10	6	4	3.99	1.08	Agreed
9	Federal government on their part should provide adequate support to the affected states by expeditiously rebuild and renovate all school buildings and facilities destroyed during the attacks	22	45	18	3	2	3.91	0.88	Agreed
10	To provide all necessary support to all those including teachers and students, who have been affected by violence which include rehabilitation and resettlement for those who have been forced to flee the violence	28	39	9	10	4	3.85	1.11	Agreed

5. Discussion

Based on research question one, the finding of the study revealed that crises has all effect on school attendance of both the teachers and students, destruction of available facilities of the schools influence the well-being of students in classroom; loss of teachers due to the crisis in the area influences the well-being of student in classroom, damaging school infrastructure can grossly reduce the availability of access to education which reduces performance, insurgents suicide bombings at school as a tactics which in turn reduce school population and affect the academic performance of students, destruction of available school facilities by insurgents leaves the educational system in a dire situation, insecurity in the state insurgents have leads to the deaths of many students, killing and abduction of students by the has been traumatic for students as they are forced to flee their homes in fear. The attack by the insurgents include fear and reduce academic performance and violence can affect attendance and learning cannot successfully occurs in an environment of fear and some of the influences of schools as insecurity constitutes a negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that Boko Haram insurgents consequently, developed threat on social well-being of students in secondary schools Potiskum local government area of Yobe State.

Based on research question two, the findings of the study also revealed that, attack on one school/locality leads to fear that any school in the area might be attacked, many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety which affect academic performance, psychosocial impact the students being kept at home which in turn affect their performance and that the targeted of the attacks of insurgents affect students ability to learn, threat of attacks persists may lead to attacks at school during insurgencies and the general State of insecurity could force to school to closed and other of the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area.

Based on research question three, the findings of the study further revealed that, insurgents (Boko Haram) and other armed groups to cease all unlawful killings, including targeted attacks on teachers, school students, state government should provide adequate security to prevent attacks on school buildings, teachers and school students/pupils, government should renovate all schools damaged in the state as a result of them violence and ensure that they are provided with adequate teaching staff, federal government on their part should provide adequate support to the affected

states by expeditiously rebuild and renovate all school buildings and facilities destroyed during the attacks and ability to provide all necessary support to all those including teachers and students, who have been affected by violence which include rehabilitation and resettlement for those who have been forced to flee the violence are some of the ways forward to the impact of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area.

6. Conclusion

The Boko Haram insurgent by singling out educational institution for concentrated attacks, have killed and maimed several students and teachers destroyed school buildings and lead to the prolonged closure of schools. This had effect of traumatizing teachers and students while retarding school enrolment and attendance in an area already poor in education service delivery.

The results of the study provide information for educational psychologists and school counselors to assist the students to overcome the emotional distress as a result of the adverse effects of insecurity on their academic performance. Teachers' on their part should employ strategies to manage students' emotional distress caused by the insecurity. Through counseling intervention, parents that are not willing to send back their sons and daughters to the affected schools may see the need for them to return their wards to schools or transfer them to other schools that are not affected by the crisis to continue with their studies. Counseling as an intervention strategy may assist an individual adjust well in the society therefore; group counseling for the youths in Nigeria is imperative to help the youth embrace peace and dialogue, because no meaningful development will take place without peace and tranquility. This study exposes to the government and public the devastating nature of insecurity and the danger that is exerting on the education system in the north-east senior secondary schools.

The impact of insecurity on students' academic performance was found to be significant in senior secondary school in Potiskum. This situation if left unchecked, will lead to permanent dropout of many students not only in Potiskum local government area but in the northern part of the country at large thereby making the available for use as political thugs and exposing them to other economic social vices. It is incumbent on the government to provide adequate and effective security personnel to all institution of learning in Yobe state, Nigeria to stop the burning of schools and constant shooting around educational institutions.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest throughout the research work, however, constructive criticism was evident at some point between researchers but a mutual understanding help in realizing the desired objectives.

Statement of informed consent

A consent letter was drafted and obtained approval from the schools head (principals) and Yobe state teaching service board before questionnaire were distributed in schools. All information retrieved were agreed to be used for the purpose of research only.

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